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Update	April 2022 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated some references in the requirement elicitation process • Added a forward reference to the FDO definition • Added references • Added a sentence regarding the "risk" of not having a full FDO definition • Renamed the demo section and try to add some minor details for the DOIP. • Removed "FDO creation workflow" subsection • Sorted the list of references • Carried out review and editorial changes

The State of Data Exchange for Research Data Centers

This report covers the first results of Measure 3, "Interfaces for data exchange processes", of the Technical Area 5, "Technical Solutions", in the KonsortSWD project. The aim of this measure is to establish an open API that allows each participant in the KonsortSWD project to exchange data or to automate the overall

process. We present our considerations and findings for an API specification, starting with the requirements identified from the KonsortSWD partners and stakeholders, our proposal in terms of technology solution, as well as a demo to illustrate bringing all the deliverables together. The resulting insights will lead to a specification that will serve as a common method to interchange data for all KonsortSWD participants. This will allow individual tools to be developed and used. Furthermore, by defining such an overarching API, federated infrastructures will be supported.

1. Introduction

Research data management practices are dictated by different factors, such as the discipline's bias; the deployed/implemented supporting technology - as manifested in repositories, data infrastructures, etc.; research policies from funders or research institutions; and so on. While this creates an inclusive environment for the representation of these different practices, adherent to the various research communities' distinct needs, the mere heterogeneity in these practices implies certain challenges to data exchange across the different domains.

As depicted in Figure 1, different players may participate in research data exchanges. In the context of Social Sciences, for example, a research institute typically designs a study, and a field institute is responsible for collecting the data. After the curating and documenting data processes, the next interaction is with data repositories, which store the data and enable its management. From this point on, there are different data access scenarios, such as (meta)data exchange between repositories (that requires a standardized content exchange), access provision to the raw data, harvest from other aggregation or indexing services that support researchers/communities, and so on. In this context, we need to consider the technical solutions applied to support different players, (meta)data, or APIs, as well as any technical challenges along the way. To enable a more seamless exchange, we utilize the FAIR principles ([Wilkinson et al., 2016](#)). Thus, creating a seamless data FAIR exchange within the KonsortSWD project requires the establishment of an exchange specification. The individual elements and metadata available should adhere to these principles to allow for more machine-actionability. This will further support the creation of tools and exchangeability among the actors.

Given the heterogeneity in research practices and the challenges that stem from it, there is a need for a common **API specification** to support the research data exchange across the different actors, practices, infrastructures, and more. The goal we address in this measure is about the requirements and stipulation of such a specification. We aim at a minimal impact on implementation among the adopting parties and attempt to address the needs that individual actors have. For the latter aspect, it is clear that extensibility for the specification needs to be planned from the very beginning. Namely, interested parties should have the means to adapt (to a certain extent) the data exchange specifications, thus participating in the broader data exchange environment that the KonsortSWD project is establishing.

Figure 1. Interfaces of data generation (KonsortSWD 2020)

This report includes the tasks we undertook and the deliverables produced as a result during the first year of the KonsortSWD project. It also serves as an initial exploration of the topic. The tasks involve:

- gathering the data exchange requirements;
- coordinating with project partners on possible implementation principles and recommendations, which also take into consideration the technical aspects of such principles;
- the initial steps towards an interface specification to address these requirements.

2. Requirements Analysis

Before engaging with any design and implementation efforts, we conducted a requirements elicitation process as a key step to understanding the project partners' practices and identifying the features that a common data exchange interface should provide. In this context, we conducted a review of existing research data infrastructures, along with expert interviews, a survey and, finally, a workshop with KonsortSWD members. Since it was important to understand the data exchange requirements in a data infrastructure context, in addition to the KonsortSWD partners, the scope for this task also included relevant practices from other research data repositories and infrastructure projects. We discuss the results of this process in Section 3 of the report ("Design Considerations").

Figure 2. The requirements gathering process techniques

In the following subsections we detail the methodology, but before we do that, we want to briefly present the rationale for the specific techniques selected for this process. [Zowghi & Coulin \(2005\)](#) provide a comprehensive list of techniques, including their applicability to different requirements gathering situations, and we will list the three techniques adopted in our work:

- Interviews: A quite common technique, they enabled us to more informally/freely form some ideas about existing data exchange practices, that we could later on focus on via the other techniques. We relied on a semi-structured interview type, which are especially suitable since they allow one to set some minimal discussion points, and allow to broaden the discussion with topics that were not initially known to the interviewer. In our case, it was important to not only get some feedback as fast as possible, but also identify potential areas to explore with the other techniques.
- Survey / Questionnaires: Are used to cover a larger number of participants. Since interviews are quite a time-consuming activity, the survey represents a suitable technique to follow up the requirements gathering process with. As noted by [Zowghi & Coulin](#), surveys are limited in terms of depth of coverage, which leads us nicely to the final technique employed for the requirements gathering process.
- Workshops: Or group works, as [Zowghi & Coulin](#) refer to them, are “particularly effective because they involve and commit the stakeholders directly and promote cooperation”. With the previous technique providing a good understanding of the practices across the participants, involvement and cooperation was precisely what we were looking for as a final component that could provide even more qualitative feedback to this process.

This section is organized according to the techniques applied for the requirement elicitation process. Starting with an exploration of practices from relevant projects, we focus on the specific requirements of the KonsortSWD project partners. For the latter, we utilized interviews, a survey and a workshop, as depicted in Figure 2.

2.1 Existing Research Data Infrastructures

As the importance of research data is on the rise, many initiatives across domains already provide Research Data Management (RDM) facilities to researchers. While they have different foci, there are features such as PID assignment or rights management that are common across all of these endeavors. Due to the measure’s structure, we start with Research Data Centers (RDCs) for research deliverables and then include larger research (data) infrastructure projects. The goal is to identify common features or

technologies across these projects, and establish a sense for a basic set of services and practices for those features. Additionally, since FAIR practices are of importance to us, we evaluate the level or maturity of the FAIR principles as adopted within these solutions.

The Educational Research Data Archive (ERDA) provided by the DIPF provides storing, sharing, analyzing and archiving functionalities for research data ([Educational Research Data Archive, 2021](#)). Researchers interested in empirical educational research can search for studies, publications, and recording modules with a REST-API¹ specification. Several parameters exist to further adapt the results when querying the interface. For example, a researcher can specify a study identifier to retrieve that particular resource or search studies based on specific vocabulary terms used to describe them. For resources of the type “studies” and “publications”, a “write” operation is provided, whereas for “recording modules” there is only a “read” operation available. The API specification includes an authentication process. Returned results are represented as JSON objects. One noteworthy feature in ERDA is the so-called “Workgroup Shared Folders”, which enables users to share their datasets within the infrastructure.

Similarly, the Research Data Repository (RADAR) supports different RDM phases² including Planning, Collecting, Analyzing, Publishing, Preserving, Sharing and Reusing and offers services for activities such as storage, annotation or citation for different research disciplines from the so-called “long tail” research ([Kraft et al., 2016](#)). This addresses the fact that mainly small teams of independent researchers and laboratories generate a wide variety of research data collections ([WYBORN et al., 2016](#)). RADAR can be used in several modes, such as the cloud, (locally) hosted, or hybrid mode (parts of it are hosted locally, and parts on the cloud). In order to allow the integration of existing systems, different endpoints support the various entities required to perform the RDM operations. These include: users, contracts (needed to get the permission to communicate with the RADAR backend), and the more data-related aspects, such as workspace, dataset, folder, and file. RADAR relies on OAuth and tokens for the authentication task to enable access to the endpoints. Similarly to ERDA, RADAR organizes the datasets in the infrastructure via the “workspace” concept.

¹ <https://erda-api.tba-hosting.de/v1/docs/>

² Please note that different communities adhere to different RDM phases; Figure 3 shows one such example.

Figure 3. Research Data Management Phases (<https://www.labfolder.com/guide-research-data-management/>)

The **VerbundFDB** as a collaboration between multiple institutions is a federated research data infrastructure focused on empirical educational research (both data and survey instruments). It provides RDM support, including data archiving and provision ([VerbundFDB, n.d.](#)). The project adopts two approaches to incorporate metadata of interest: (i) via its Data Management Module, which enables RDCs and their curators to oversee this process, and (ii) harvesting via the da|ra registry ([Harzenetter et al., 2018](#)). Moreover, its metadata is indexed (and made searchable) based on the DDI, DataCite, and da|ra metadata schemas, with a core set of mandatory metadata elements (a typical practice for metadata from different resources and of different “shapes”). This project has recently relied on the ERDA interface for data exchange³, and provides a GUI for its users, especially for the search feature. Another project, similar in scope to VerbundFDB, is the **ExploreData** project from GESIS. Even though it is only used internally at the institution, it provides similar traits to the ones we just discussed. Focusing mainly on search, it targets research data from social sciences based on different granularities or combinations of studies, variables, and questions, across different languages ([Explore Data, n.d.](#)). Moreover, the metadata are represented according to the DDI 3.2 standard⁴ and indexed with ElasticSearch to support the search scenarios. JSON is the chosen format for the representation of the search results.

³ The complete API documentation: <https://api.forschungsdaten-bildung.de/v1/docs>.

⁴ <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-Lifecycle/3.2/>

The **GAIA-X** initiative was also launched to offer data and services, triggered by the industry's (data) perspective and needs. As such, it was designed to enable security and data sovereignty during data exchanges, and to include support beyond academia while targeting both EU companies and citizens (Braud et al., 2021). Machine-actionability is one of the architectural guidelines of this infrastructure, as all GAIA-X artifacts are machine-readable, with APIs enabling interaction of any kind for both humans and machines alike (DE-CIX et al., 2020). The infrastructure relies on a Self-Description ontology to organize all the Gaia-X entities in a collection, and JSON-LD as an exchange format (Gaia-X TC Working Group Provider et al., 2021). However, the model's properties go beyond machine-actionability. It further offers schemas for mandatory and optional properties and relations. This is how scenarios requiring a broader scope for both data and infrastructure can be addressed.

Different infrastructure projects focus on and address different requirements that correspond to RDM practices. We reviewed several undertakings in order to establish an understanding of some of the challenges they tackle and the approaches they employ. As a result, we summarize the following observations. While several technologies for the implementation of APIs (especially Web APIs) exist, the RESTful architecture still remains the most popular, even beyond the presented endeavors. The “conceptual models” behind the varying domain of interest show different degrees of FAIRness. In any case, we did not encounter any adoption of the FAIR Digital Object (FDO) as a model for interface operations, which could be characterized as a “coupling of metadata, data, and persistent identifiers” (Schwardmann, 2020). This is a brief description of the FDO, of course, and we provide a more detailed discussion on it later in the report (see Section 3.2).

2.2 Interviews

Considering the large number of stakeholders in the project, we wanted to get an initial impression of the existing data exchange practices within the KonsortSWD community. To this end, we decided to identify potential issues and challenges - regardless if they originate from user requirements, available technologies, or any other cause. We chose interviews with a set of guiding (semi-structured) questions as a method to reach these goals.

Due to limitations regarding the participant availability and the COVID-19 pandemic, only a small number of participants (n=5, 4 from DIPF⁵, and 1 from GESIS) participated in the interviews. None of the interviewees was involved in the KonsortSWD project. The interviews were neither recorded nor transcribed, but they were accompanied by note taking in order to correctly summarize the findings.

The management of rights in terms of data security and copyright was an important topic raised and discussed with a DIPF representative. Rights management was defined as a key requirement for an infrastructure that deals with data exchange scenarios. When it comes to access rights, different levels need to be distinguished. Granting access to a certain level depends on the privacy and anonymization

⁵ DIPF | Leibniz Institute for Research and Information in Education

required for that level. The highest or more restrictive level requires users to confirm their identity through a formal institution, e.g., by post office (the “POST-Idend”, in Germany), whereas free data access represents the lowest restrictive access level. An access request starts with filling out a (web) form and continues with different manual steps for verifying the qualification of the requestor. If successful, the adequate access rights are manually assigned. Moreover, interviewees from the VerbundFDB and FDZ Bildung data centers stated the sharing of metadata and enabling a search in (ideally) all RDCs as essential requirements. In addition, they consider it especially important to support researchers accessing datasets that might reside across various RDCs. The latter scenario is becoming increasingly frequent due to the adoption of federated infrastructures.

The GESIS representative provided valuable feedback to our requirements analysis activities, including data exchange use cases, perceived values, and potential challenges. One of the key motivations for infrastructures to collaborate is the lack of funds for developing new services. This is one reason for an exchange of data and services with existing infrastructure services. While writing the report, GESIS is engaged with identifying the requirements for a more fine-grained DOI assignment in the context of social studies. This would enable use cases that could affect data (re)usability and align well with the requirement of searching data and data access across RDCs. Furthermore, with such fine-grained DOIs available, researchers will be enabled to cite individual elements instead of general studies.

Another aspect that we discussed among all participants was the type of operations intended for the KonsortSWD data exchange interface. Especially the question whether the interface should only support read-only operations, or allow write access as well, was raised. In any case, write operations have been considered as a crucial part of the KonsortSWD operations. However, additional security considerations should be included in order to avoid modifying or deleting information - on purpose or by accident. One use case derived from this discussion is the dataset repackaging (see Section 3), which will enable users to (re)use, remix, and publish/upload datasets at different granularities.

As a result of the interviews, we identified the following use cases:

1. Authentication of users using partially secure methods to ensure validity and research interests.
2. Individual rights management for the RDCs to fulfill their contracts.
3. Search for variables, questions, etc.: This enables users to not only search based on the study, but at a more fine-grained level, such as a study question or variable.
4. Cite a variable: Once more finer-grained information is available (see the previous point), other use cases can surface. For example, in addition to only being able to cite a study, now researchers would be able to cite at a more specific level, such as a variable.
5. Connect different variables, questions, etc., and repackage them as a new dataset: In this case, the researchers can retrieve and combine parts from studies - even approach it in a cross-domain manner - and connect results from one domain to another one.

2.3 Survey

The third step within the requirement elicitation process is the survey that we conducted with the partner RDCs within the KonsortSWD project. The goal of the survey is in line with that of the two previous techniques, namely understanding the current technical practices of data exchange and any other relevant requirements from our stakeholders. The target audience targets a broader range of KonsortSWD partners, including members in different roles in this consortium, not necessarily limited to that of IT (or API design and implementation) functions and participants. Thus, the results are not supposed to provide a comprehensive list of technical requirements. To get a broader understanding of the current data exchange use cases, we connected the initial findings from the interviews with the survey results.

The survey was designed based on the prior findings from the background research and the interviews⁶. The partner RDCs were invited by email containing a link to the survey tool. We addressed 61 recipients from 39 RDCs. The survey was open for 11 days, lasting from April 26 to May 7, 2021. In total, we received 22 (36%) survey submissions from the partners, of which 6 were incomplete.

The survey contained 13 questions organized in six sections, and covered different research data management (RDM) topics presented in section 2.1 ([Existing Research Data Infrastructures](#)). The focus was on interaction patterns and access methods that arise when following the common phases of a research data lifecycle. The first section gathered general information of the participants, such as their (institutional) affiliation, job position and experience. This acknowledgment was used to rate the quality of the answers, thus the resulting requirements and practices. The other five sections covered the following topics:

- **Data repository** Information about the repository solution used, its interface (and supported operations), whether it was developed in-house, open-source, etc.;
- **Data access** How do users access (which operations) the research data collection, and at what granularity (dataset level, data point level, discipline-specific access, etc.)?
- **Data Create/Read/Update/Delete operations** Which one of these operations does your institutional repository interface support? Anything else beyond this set?
- **Access control** Is access control required for your research data? If yes, for which operations and what metadata are required to enforce it?
- **Metadata** This topic covers the metadata standard the interface supports for the datasets.

The complete survey responses are available online⁷ and the questionnaire is represented in Appendix II. In the following, the more critical findings or practices are summarized. The technology, granularity and

⁶ You can find the Google Form at https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeGx_4zERHcCGmzVYSG4gbwcC6RPwrQpCJeiA0zRn_cSplug/viewform, whereas a textual representation in Appendix II of the report.
⁷https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1gXP9loCSYX4oyw5NRf3r85BqUqW41qxBm9_3XrcRMpM/edit?usp=sharing

modification possibilities among the RDCs are shown in Figure 4. Note that the number of responses deviates for each question.

Figure 4. Individual responses visualized as bar plots. The upper left chart shows the availability of technologies to access the data in an RDC. The one in the upper right shows the granularity that a user can extract information using the technology stack. The lower chart shows the availability to access and modify the data in general (Create, Read, Update, Delete).

Based on all the answers, we can summarize the findings as follows:

- The majority of the participants (38% with more than 10 years, and 31% with 6 to 8 years of experience) is well-versed with research data management tasks. This tells us that the identified practices and required data exchange features in the survey are highly relevant to the KonsortSWD data exchange interface.

- 60% of the participants reported that their institution uses an externally developed research data repository. This implies that these repositories and their interfaces would play an important role in defining the common exchange specification for the project.
- Participants rely on different interfaces while accessing the research data collections in their repositories/institutions, including HTML/Web, REST APIs, or protocols such as OAI-PMH. There are still more “traditional interfaces”, such as remote execution, via Compact Disks (CD) that contain the desired data, or via a guest machine for the more sensitive data. In any case, this provides additional information on the way different KonsortSWD partners interact with their data collections; this is also important to consider for the data exchange interface to support a broader selection of current interfaces as possible, or at least provide minimal technology barrier when shifting to the KonsortSWD interface specification.
- When accessing (meta)data collections, in almost 80% of the answers, the user needs to be able to list all the available datasets and their metadata (in almost 90% of the cases) and search and filter datasets based on certain criteria (data provider, institution, domain, etc.). In around 11% of the cases, the user needs to have a more fine-grained access to the datasets, such as searching for particular variables or concepts in a study.
- When it comes to data granularity access, the common practice (in 88% of the cases) is to locate datasets based on the typical descriptive metadata, such as title, date, author, etc.. In contrast, a smaller group of participants (25%) needs access based on dataset variables.
- Reading metadata is necessary for all respondents; metadata update is the second most popular feature (71%); metadata creation is practiced by 57% of the respondents; and almost 30% of the surveyed persons reported metadata deletion is an operation that their (RDC) interface supports.
- Access control is another aspect covered by the survey. 60% of the respondents report that access control is present in their repositories and important to them; 40% have free access in their collections/repositories, thereby implying no need for any access policies for their collections.
- Once (meta)data is in a repository, it often becomes important for users to export or import them. Based on the survey, 50% of the respondents report an export feature, whereas 67% of them report an import feature in their research data repository.

Based on the results of the survey and the interviews, we can further specify the requirements for the datasets and the access to them. The search for available datasets, the inspection of study metadata, as well as a more fine-grained access to the datasets (such as on the level of variables) are relevant use cases when it comes to the search for data. In addition to search, metadata creation and updates are use cases that should be supported by the intended API.

2.4 Workshop

Exploring the approaches of data exchange interfaces in existing research data infrastructure projects (see [2.1 Existing Research Data Infrastructures](#)) and getting familiar with the research data practices of KonsortSWD partners (see [2.2 Interviews](#) and [2.3 Survey](#)) helped provide an overview of the state of the art practice. As a result, it became possible to initiate deeper and more technical discussions of the

requirements needed for an interface specification, able to support different data exchange scenarios. A workshop with several KonsortSWD members and practitioners was chosen as a format to foster these discussions.

2.4.1 Workshop Scope

We structured the workshop with the following aspects in mind: **objectives**, **participants**, and **expectations**, which were communicated to the participants beforehand. They are briefly presented below.

Workshop **objectives** included:

- Exploring the benefits of data exchange between infrastructures based on a (new) common interface specification;
- Selecting use cases suitable for further development towards an NFDI interface. The plan is to adopt Fair Digital Objects (FDO) as part of this interface;
- Analyzing use cases with regards to standardization and automation options in order to draw generalizable conclusions for further work in KonsortSWD;
- Identifying partners to help set up test and demo versions and showcase the selected use cases;
- Building a network of experts with whose help, good cooperation, and mutual support, all the needs in the environment of KonsortSWD and NFDI can be optimally served;

Participants targeted for the workshop included:

- Those whose job relates/includes or is interested to know more about API design and/or data exchange between research data infrastructures;
- Anyone involved with the administration of research data infrastructure on a day-to-day basis.
- Those with decision-making power over technical implementations or planned investments.
- Members of other KonsortSWD working groups with overlapping topics with ours.
- Members of working groups who want to have an overview and develop their networking with other work groups.

Expectations of the workshop included:

- A list of use cases to continue to work on;
- An idea of how to implement an API together with volunteers from the network;

2.4.2 Workshop deliverables

Given the number of participants (N=22), we decided that having smaller groups of participants in separate “virtual rooms” would enable a more effective discussion. These discussions were organized via 3 groups where participants with different roles or job responsibilities - thus different perspectives - would meet to discuss the requirements of interconnecting between the different KonsortSWD players. As far as the technical organization of the groups goes, we relied on Google Jamboard as the tool of choice, where we created the “space” for these three groups to note their recommendations, issues or existing approaches.

Group #	Key requirements
Group 1	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) based on any system (DOI, URN, Handle, PID); 2. Possibility to version the metadata on changes and the entities themselves; 3. Combine and integrate different entities (Question, Variables, video snippets, audio recordings) from a dataset; 4. API operations: (1) Get data, (2) Get metadata, (3) Get aggregations. <p>Questions raised:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Why provide a fine-grained identification (citation)? ● One can always point to a study and specify (in a paper) the variables, etc.?
Group 2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Metadata should be the link between objects related to more than data and also include RDCs, scientits, journals, and other players in the field. Few players are doing this in the field, but even more players want to do this. 2. PID assignment to an object related to a person: This is very interesting, because it means finding a person in real life. The assignment and the resolution of the location should ensure this. 3. An important requirement is that of the rights and access management. Each RDC has a dedicated granularity of access and contract issues. These workflows are very heterogeneous. There is a great motivation to change it to a new design, but players are afraid about the great/potential challenges that may arise. 4. Using DOIs for cross domain linking.
Group 3	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tools for editing metadata 2. Lifecycle / Workflow to support creation of research data 3. GDPR and aggregated data <p>Question raised:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How to enable easy adoption for smaller RDCs?

Table 1. Requirements from the three groups of the workshop

We gathered the information stored within the Google Jamboards along with notes taken during the workshop to consolidate the results and requirements. Table 1 presents the main requirements that the three groups discussed during the workshop, either as direct, explicit requirements, or as distilled outcomes from our discussion. In addition to these requirements, we also identified 4 use cases (see Appendix A): Retrieve (FAIR) FDOs, Data upload, Data repackaging and Single Sign On. Data linking will be an additional use case that will inherently benefit from using FDOs. Furthermore, we extracted the main

question that arose during the discussions in the individual groups, which are embedded within the given use cases.

Given these use cases, we derive the following priorities for a potential implementation:

1. FDO retrieval
Enabling access to an FDO and presenting simple interactions based on the available data is a very good example to show the potential behind FDOs. Hence this has been identified as the highest priority use case.
2. Data repackaging
The next logical step after the data retrieval is to allow users or systems to add to/combine/merge them with other datasets to provide new data collections. This can be seen as a bootstrap method to convert or provide additional views on the existing data sets.
3. Data upload
Finally, uploading a new data set is the final puzzle piece. With this use case, a complete data lifecycle will be available and an API will exist to utilize the data available.

The *Single Sign On* use case, while being requested frequently, is not on our priority list. The main goal of our project focuses on the definition of an API and not on the service-level implementations or considerations. A single-sign-on methodology is an enabling technology for a lot of the features, but, from an API level, it can simply be mocked or substituted once an implementation is available. Furthermore, the topic is also addressed by other measures within the KonsortSWD and even on an NFDI scope.

3. Design Considerations

The technology to rely on and the way to model the objects in our data exchange scenarios are another point of consideration. We utilize the results from the requirement analysis to derive a solution that strives to honor the identified user preferences. We explored a few data exchange options focusing on needs and available resources, and present promising technology stacks to support our design considerations in this measure. Earlier in the report we mentioned the role of the FAIR principles in this measure. To foster the use of FAIR principles, we embed the concept of FDOs at the very core of our API design.

3.1 Technology Considerations

There are a lot of possibilities for an interchange of data between services, service providers and service consumers. Examples of data exchange technology include Web services (or APIs, e.g. Simple Object Access Protocol (SOAP), REST, and GraphQL); Extract, Transform, and Load (ETL); file transfer; Remote Procedure Call (RPC), referring to non-web/HTTP implementations; event-based/brokered messaging; or data streaming (Charest & Rogers, 2020). In the same work, the authors provide use cases that best suit the presented methods. In this context, another option that is quite relevant to our work, part of the Web

services data exchange method and especially in relation to the FDOs, is the Digital Object Interface Protocol (DOIP) ([DONA, n.d.](#)).

Having considered multiple options, we believe that the APIs fulfill each of the categories' strong points, thus it represents our technology recommendations within this measure. Table 2 shows some of the use cases in which APIs excel. For each use case, we provide the relevance to the data exchange interface requirements in KonsortSWD. Please note that we only reviewed the use cases for which APIs have the strongest suitability and left out the ones for which APIs are ranked as “medium” or “low” in terms of applicability.

Typical use cases for APIs	Applicability to KonsortSWD data exchange interface
<p><i>The data is required in multiple formats</i></p>	<p>It is not uncommon for infrastructure projects to serve different players with different formats for a requested resource. For example, whereas text-based/HTML could be preferred by one group, another might prefer XML or JSON formats, and so on. So far, JSON is the format being adopted in KonsortSWD, but new formats can become part of the user requirements in the future.</p>
<p><i>The data is used in a client front-end</i></p> <p>If the receiving system is front-facing, such as a web browser or similar agent, then REST APIs are a reasonable choice.</p>	<p>The interface should support different modes of client front-end, including web browsers, stand-alone applications, etc.</p>
<p><i>The data supports a feature</i></p> <p>The data is being used to support a 'feature' and supports a specific need.</p>	<p>In our case operating on FDOs is such a feature, one that should enable retrieval of the datasets (and their attributes) of interest.</p>
<p><i>The data is frequently requested</i></p> <p>If access to the most up-to-date version of the data is a requirement, then some form of synchronous remote procedure call or API will be required.</p>	<p>Users of the data exchange interface are expected to frequently request FDO instances - as new datasets become available or new users join in - so providing means to access a specific - including the most up-to-date version of an FDO - becomes important.</p>
<p><i>The data changes frequently</i></p> <p>API methods more easily support transactional updates to avoid constant</p>	<p>The model that we adopt to represent the resources in this project is suitable for data changes of any scale. In this project, this is especially expected during data reusability, whereas users/researchers can extend/mix data(sub)sets to create new</p>

bulk resynchronization and are likely better options in this scenario.	(FDO) instances. In this context, any bulk resynchronization operations would not be applicable.
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Table 2. Typical use cases for APIs as means for Data exchange methods for KonsortSWD data exchange interface (Adopted from [Charest & Rogers, 2020](#))

In the context of the KonsortSWD project, the API needs to be easy to implement by all interested parties. From the *architectural pattern* view, REST ([What is REST, 2021](#)) is one of the well known and best supported styles, and represents data resources in a simple manner. It is based on the HTTP *protocol* to access resources via URL-encoded parameters and the use of multiple *formats* to transmit data (JSON, XML, etc.). The interface will benefit from additional features, such as security and session management. What's more, relying on the REST architectural style, the JSON format, and the HTTP(S) protocol is a well-established combination.

Some of the RDCs have implemented a REST API already. They can contribute with their skills in tasks such as collaboratively implementing initial use cases, providing adoption suggestions from their past projects, and so on. Moreover, when it comes to the exchange format of choice, REST and JSON are very popular options for common data encapsulation. SOAP and XML are popular too, and XML is used by some RDC's, but XML's main purpose is as a document markup. It is recommended always to prefer XML whenever document markup and metadata are an essential part of data and cannot be split. In our model, we prefer metadata encapsulating data for better machine processing ([JSON vs. XML, 2021](#)). GraphQL, on the other hand, has the advantage of fewer endpoints and the possibility to adapt the response of a request. While fewer endpoints and higher flexibility benefit good maintenance, availability and experience is a limiting factor. To conclude, REST remains the best fit given its wide acceptance and easy adoption.

3.2 Modeling considerations

[Wittenburg et al. \(2019\)](#) emphasize the need for a model for digital entities, with certain features, such as persistent identification, entity attribute, and operations description - represented in FAIR Digital Objects (FDO). The concept of FDOs is an extension of the concept of Digital Objects (DOs) introduced by Kahn & Wilenski in the 90s and then taken up by RDA (GEDE) and GO FAIR. The idea of a DO is to capture the core information about a data object (such as PIDs) in one place while encapsulating the diversity of data types and technical details. **FAIR** DOs (FDOs) aim at adding explicit semantics to the DO model (by taking into account Linked Data (LD) approaches, for example) to enable machines to interpret the semantic description of DOs in the sense of the FAIR principles ([Wilkinson et al., 2016](#)). However, there is currently no commonly agreed technical specification on FDOs. Thus, the challenge still is to find the right formal model for it. There is very much ongoing work on that issue, such as the FDO Framework proposed by Luiz Bonino from GO-FAIR ([The FDO Framework, Luiz Bonino and Peter Wittenberg, 2019](#)) and RO-Crate ([Peter Sefton et al., 2021](#)), and there is currently considerable discussion within the FDO Forum ([fairdo.org](#))

which has emerged in early 2021 from previous initiatives (the much-referenced Paris Workshop on FDOs, the GO FAIR Implementation Network on Cross-domain Interoperability, GO Inter, etc.).

Accordingly, in the context of our interface requirements, we see FDOs as a machine-actionable interoperable representation of KonsortSWD data. By this, it is the base entity for data storage and exchange between RDCs and scientists. The Digital Object Interface Protocol (DOIP) Specification regulates the interaction between clients and DOIP services that offer DOs ([DOIP, 2018](#)). This is an important aspect for a model that adopts DOs as one of the building blocks of the interface. Given the still ongoing specification work on FDOs, it remains an ongoing task of following those specifications as they arise, or make the necessary assumptions about the FDOs in the context of our interface. This is especially important since our communities need to be able to adhere to these, FDO and FDO-like specifications. Thus, we plan to iteratively adjust our FDO model and implementation according to specifications provided by the FDO Forum. However, we must also reserve the right to go beyond existing FDO specifications or protocols, such as DOIP, which, so far, does not consider approaches from the Semantic Web and the Linked Data community, if the use cases to be implemented require it. In the following, we present our approach to implement the FDO concept in the KonsortSWD use cases.

A DO instance, regardless of its structure, can be interpreted as a dataset. In this context, the requirements to publish it - according to the current research data practices - are known. We, however, also include the FAIR principles ([Wilkinson et al., 2016](#)), with their focus on findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of published data.

[De Smedt et al. \(2020\)](#) present an abstraction model for an FDO as a “self-contained, typed, machine-actionable data package”. Figure 5 shows the features and components of this model. The first layer of the model is about the persistent identifier (PID), allowing for its unique identification. The next layer defines the operations this (FDO) object supports. The following two layers - metadata and bit sequence - map to the usual approach communities adopt to describe their data collections - both in terms of data and metadata.

To adopt the FDO model for the requirements of our data exchange interface, we make the following assumptions:

- The PID is pre-existing: Assignment and management of PIDs will be supported by another measure in the project. Until a specific implementation at the back-end is chosen, any identifier is considered valid.
- The operations are pre-existing: Operations could be metadata to describe how to process data, functions in a virtual runtime environment to provide processing instructions, etc.
- The metadata layer consists of a set of predefined elements: There will be cross-domain and domain-specific metadata elements, supporting a different breadth and depth of a domain or discipline. Initially we will start with more common generic metadata elements from known metadata

standards, such as the Dublin Core metadata initiative⁸, and include the more disciplinary metadata elements as necessary as we receive more feedback and see more feedback from the community.

- The bit sequence (Content): It represents the actual data and must be machine-actionable based on the metadata and functions.

Figure 5. The FAIR Digital Object model (<https://www.mdpi.com/2304-6775/8/2/21>)

The FDO initiative is quite important in that it brings together two important aspects - a set of relatively new principles (part of FAIR), and a more concrete representation of objects (reflected in the Digital Objects (DO) initiative) (Zowghi & Coulin, 2005). Given this, it is clear that time is required until different communities adopt and concretize these principles and their corresponding representation, and ultimately achieve a broader, agreed-upon understanding of it. In any case, by relying on such an emerging concept, still in the process of specification, we run the risk of not having a full FDO definition as the basis to do so.

While we experiment and engage with the FDO as an emerging, innovative, and value-adding model, in order to manage any potential risk that stems from a lacking (FDO) specification, we (a) assume a set of minimal common features, and (b) plan for extensibility of such a model. In this way, we do not commit too much in a proposal that has the chance to change in the future, and for any new aspects that do change - and get standardized - we should be able to address by extending our current model. In any case, being an important part of our work, we remain committed to participating and following the corresponding (standardization) bodies, such as the FDO Forum⁹, engaged in standardizing the FDO model.

In addition to adopting a model that brings valuable and contemporary features together, it is essential to emphasize the benefits of such adoption by an interface that targets the KonsortSWD community. We expect a potential to move from the access limited by individual RDCs to an FDO-based access level. This means access is managed at the level of an FDO instance, which leads to dataset reusability at different granularities, the provision of machine actionability, and enabling citation features for the targeted collections.

⁸ <https://www.dublincore.org/>

⁹ <https://fairdo.org/>

4. Implementation based on FDOs

We now showcase how our findings from Sections 2 and 3 come together and contribute to a solution. Within this section we present two approaches based on the use cases provided in the requirement elicitation process. First we present how to integrate the FDO into existing data and provide a uniform access layer. The second example shows how new FDOs are to be created.

4.1 Retrieve FDOs from existing Research Data Centers

This showcase demonstrates the ability to use DOIP to retrieve data located in a KonsortSWD RDC. It currently provides access to 2 data sources:

1. **Gesis Explore Data:** Explore Data is an internal GESIS project to develop a user-friendly, web-based search and browse portal for social science research data across studies, variables, and questions. It enables textual searches across different entities and multilingual documentation based on the DDI metadata scheme. The portal also allows browsing metadata via facets, such as language, geographical areas, periods, etc. The ElasticSearch index, powering the search, is based entirely on the DDI 3.2 standard.
2. **DIPF studies data:** At DIPF, the Research Data Education Alliance (VerbundFDB) and the Research Data Centre for Education (FDZ Bildung) store scientific data and prepare them for re-usage, offering educational researchers a reliable repository for the data they have assessed. The DIPF studies data provides central access to information and search options on available studies and data.

In the DOIP specification, a DO is defined very closely to our idea of an FDO. Utilizing a mapping from DOs to FDOs allows to integrate DOIP resources. As a first step, we integrate a DOIP client into an API gateway and implement a simple FDO retrieval given a DOI. For the demonstration, the PID naming schema is defined by DOIP, which is a limitation. In further developmental steps, there must be a metadata field that is also compatible with other protocols.

Figure 7: Demo: Adopting DOIP for data retrieval

As shown in figure 7, the retrieval process starts with the input of a PID. The API then internally invokes the DOIP Client which connects with the DOIP Server. The actual work happens within the server, where the DOIP ID is mapped to the indices of both connected services, the GESIS ExploreData and that of DIPF Data. Finally, the server requests the actual dataset from the RDC and returns it to the client.

The Demo provides us an experience of using DOIP to exchange data in the form of digital objects and demonstrates the ability to use DOIP to exchange data stored in the selected RDCs. We also learned from the demo how to extend digital objects to create FAIR digital objects (FDOs) which are a logical extension of digital objects.

The demonstration is a starting point to identify solutions to open questions and known challenges. A first step is done towards a more extensive infrastructure system by connecting two RDCs in a common API to retrieve data. We intend to extend the list of partners in the future, while adding the other use cases to our demo. One such example could be to link FDOs - based on certain criteria - from different RDCs representing various kinds of entities, representing the resulting, novel object as an FDO too.

In the demonstration, the FDOs are a logical extension of the DOs used together with the DOIP (see Figure 8 below). In particular, FDOs are DOs with a Persistent Identifier (PID). The PID is also of a specific type. The type identifies the set of available operations. The following diagram demonstrates this logical extension of the DO to FDO.

Figure 8. FDO as a logical extension of DO.

Below are two FDO examples with a PID of type DOI and URL.

Figure 9. FDO with PID of type DOI

Figure 10. FDO with PID of type URL

In Figure 9, the FDO has a PID of value “10.4232/1.0068”. The PID is of type DOI. The type DOI indicates that “10.4232/1.0068” is a DOI which can be resolved by a Handle system. In Figure 10, the FDO has a PID of value “<https://api.forschungsdaten-bildung.de/v1/studies/269>”. The PID is of type URL. The type URL indicates that “<https://api.forschungsdaten-bildung.de/v1/studies/269>” is a URL which is the address of a unique resource on the Web.

4.2 FDO creation workflow

As mentioned before, there is not yet a distinct way to create FDOs. For example, the process can start by setting a (temporary) PID and working towards setting the bit sequence as the last FDO layer. Conversely, one can also build an FDO instance starting from the bit sequence and complete all the details, concluding with a PID assignment.

In the following workflow, we present the current approach to create an FDO. We initially build an FDO instance and then complete all the details (c.f. Figure 6). The final step assigns a PID and thereby renders an FDO immutable:

- Start with a template scenario from any RDC of a desired domain. A local application or a web service could be used to manage the instance attributes. This results in an initial set of metadata fields and a skeleton of an FDO for further processing.
- The FDO is then extended with individual metadata or data as a bit stream. The selection of the individual (meta)data depends on the intention of the FDO, and ultimately is the choice of its creator.
- The next step is a validation of the FDO. Its metadata - or any other FDO layer for that matter - can be validated and/or enriched by RDCs. Also, rights management should be considered for the FDO at this point.
- To complete and finalize the FDO, a PID is required. The most suitable way is to upload the FDO to an RDC (see the last steps in data upload of Figure 6). The RDC validates the FDO and assigns it a PID. The FDO is completed and available based on the metadata.

Figure 6. An FDO creation: A data upload use case

Given a finalized FDO, different operations could be available. We see some distinctive features when conducting CRUD-like (Create/Read/Update/Delete) operations on FDOs:

- **Create:** An FDO can be organized according to the layers in Figure 5. Its parts can be instantiated following the workflow we just presented, but it should be noted that other ways, thus workflows, to instantiate an FDO exist. The PID layer is of special importance: it binds the metadata description, available operations, and the actual data (bit sequence) into a self-contained object. The FDO cannot be changed, thus supporting users through activities such as citation (ensure they are citing the right resource) or reuse (ensure they are reusing the right resource).
- **Read:** A local/client application or one on the server-side accesses/reads an FDO to retrieve certain information from it.
- **Update:** There are a few questions that arose from the requirements that relate to citability, versioning, and linking. Although we do not answer these questions in this report, it is helpful to consider them as requirements for the API design. Assigning a PID to an FDO resource is one of the main challenges. Once assigned, it represents a complete, unalterable object. However, there are cases where metadata is linked and needs to be embedded into an existing FDO. This information then also needs to be versioned and immutable to ensure its validity. The simple retrieval of information can then result in a cascade of requests.
- **Delete:** This operation could be the most complex part of the CRUD operations. Such could be the case when deleting cloned FDOs or (parts of) their layers. Per our design, changing the PID assignment is impossible. To permanently delete or replace an FDO, a “tombstone” with hints to the deleted information is placed. This exact implementation remains an open question and needs to be addressed in the future.

The main benefit of adding these additional layers and including the FAIR principles is manifold. As an FDO is an instance consisting of mapped PID and (meta)data and operations, it can be stored in any repository. Furthermore, it can be freely moved or copied around across different repositories. The data and meta-information is no longer bound to a specific RDC. Finally, the PID layer guarantees that the right FDO is being accessed by using a proper PID location resolution.

5. Conclusion

The first steps in defining an interface that would support data exchange operations in KonsortSWD started with identifying the requirements such an interface needs to provide for the corresponding communities. We began reviewing related projects - research data infrastructures from a similar domain (and scope) - to study their approaches to supporting data exchange operations. To consider the specifics of the KonsortSWD communities, we proceeded with qualitative (interviews) and quantitative (survey) requirements determination techniques to establish an initial understanding of the needs of these

communities. These findings set the stage for a workshop with community representatives who are more involved with designing and using data exchange interfaces. The workshop provided great feedback in our later tasks, such as the use case definition or data exchange pattern identification. Due to the community involvement, we also collected an implicit prioritization of the use cases.

The outcomes of these activities enabled us to match a suitable data exchange pattern with a (FAIR) data model that would support cross-repository operations. For the latter, we chose the Digital Object, and to make research data FAIR, we included the FDO model from the very beginning. Furthermore, we demonstrated the adoption of DOIP to enable the operations based on FDO, in this case for retrieving a dataset. This served as a relevant first step towards implementing the use cases.

At the same time, there is an increasing adoption of the Open Science movement. Having the FAIR principles applied to the Digital Objects, i.e., FDOs, and ensuring their usage as a model for a data exchange interface seems like a move in the right direction. This seems to provide a more granular, readable, and machine-actionable unit of resources in the research community. The demonstration part serves as a base to better understand these combinations and further explore their possibilities. We expect other endeavors to face similar requirements and to benefit from our findings across domains.

Our next steps include activities to make our findings available for a broader audience. We will extend the demonstration with additional use case implementations with our collaborators. To be precise, we plan to focus on the following:

- Install a website as an information portal for partners: They will be able to track all our progress, including measuring deliverables.
- Install a live demonstration for the FDO example: Keep the network of collaborators engaged with any implementation. Since our first demonstration includes the DOIP adoption for one scenario, making a publicly available running instance is the first step in this direction.
- Setup a reference instance for testing the interface, accessible for external partners.
- Contact collaboration partners: During our requirements determination process, we have built a network of potential collaborators who see value in the KonsortSWD services and are interested in working with us on design and implementation aspects. Some of them already expressed their commitment during the workshop event, and they were the first ones to be invited. This report will be shared with them (and the survey and interview participants) to give them more details about our findings and potentially peak the interests of both the existing and new collaborators.
- Design a workflow to adopt more use cases: Appendix A provides the first 4 use cases we identified, considering priorities for the implementation plan. This is by no means a final list; we keep identifying new use cases, either as a direct request from the communities, or as a result of our explorations.
- Implement the use cases based on the implicit prioritization extracted (*Retrieve FDO*, *Data Upload* and *Data Repackaging*, see Section 2) within the requirement elicitation process and provide feedback to the community.

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Appendix I

General Features and Use Cases

Section 2 provided a rich set of requirements, which we used to identify the use cases and their scenarios, and considered the ones we should start implementing. On the latter point, during our requirements gathering process, we used the chance to network and identified participants interested to collaborate with us in implementing these use cases. Based on the feedback from Section 2, the identified use cases are discussed. A general note about the use cases: The user in these use cases can either be a researcher or a(n RDC or its) service. For both cases, it is assumed that they have the required credentials to carry out the use case tasks. For the sake of completion, we have provided a few cases where such exceptions happen and extended the flow accordingly.

Retrieve a FAIR Digital Object

In this use case, the user retrieves the FDO of the given PID. The API retrieves the FDO from the data set of the PID and displays it to the user in the predefined format. The result is a uniquely identified digital object that allows for machine-actionable operations and further use, e.g. in the creation of new FDOs.

Primary actor	User who has the required credentials such as username/password.
Input	PID (Persistent Identifier)
Output	The FDO of the given PID is displayed to the user.
Brief description	The user has a valid credential and the user wants to retrieve the FDO of a given PID.
Normal flow of events	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user provides a PID as a search criteria 2. The API identifies the corresponding FDO

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. The API checks the credentials required to access the FDO 4. The retrieved FDO is displayed to the user, including the required authorization.
Alternate flows	2.1 The FDO of the given PID is not found, and the API returns the necessary message.

Table 2. Use case 1: FDO retrieval

Data Upload

This use case derives from the KonsortSWD proposal (p. 107): “The specification builds on DDI and will focus both on the interaction among stakeholders and the submission of (meta)data.”. It enables a user - both researcher or an RDC - to upload a dataset. In any case, the dataset can originate from a local or individual storage (more common for researchers, although they could also rely on cloud or other storage-dedicated services), or that of an RDC. We assume that the dataset is FDO compliant.

Primary actor	Researcher / Research Data Center user
Input	Dataset (meta)data and target storage
Output	Link to the uploaded dataset
Brief description	The user - a researcher or an RDC - uploads a dataset. In this process, she specifies/selects the dataset and the destination for its upload, which in our context usually is an RDC, although this may change. Given the needed authorization, she uploads the dataset to the RDC of her choice. An access link (PID) for the (FDO) uploaded resource is provided upon successful operation.
Normal flow of events	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user triggers the “data upload” event via the interface. 2. The user provides the dataset to be uploaded - a local file, a networked storage solution, cloud solution, RDC, etc.; <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. The “Create FDO” use case is invoked with the uploaded dataset as input. 3. The user provides the target storage for the selected dataset. 4. The user receives an access link (PID) to the dataset in the target storage solution.
Alternate flows	2.1 There is an issue with locating the dataset. The use case prompts the user to specify the dataset location.

	<p>3.1 There is an issue with locating the target storage solution. The use case prompts the user to specify a target storage solution.</p> <p>4.1. The target storage solution does not grant permission for the data upload.</p>
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Table 3. Use case 2: (FDO) Data upload

Data Repackaging

Often users are interested in certain parts of a dataset. This not only provides fine-grained access capabilities, but also enables (re)use of and access to different parts of a dataset. In any case, the outcomes themselves are also FDOs. In this context, scenarios for combining different parts of datasets include the following:

- Fine-grained access: (Parts of) Studies, variables, questions, concepts, etc., and not necessarily deal with the whole study regardless of your dataset needs.
- Within- or cross-domain (re)use: Connect parts of a dataset (study, variable, concept, etc.) with parts of another study, be it from the same, or another domain.

With PIDs available to target specific parts of a dataset (fine-grained access of studies, such as at the question, variable, concept, etc., level), there will be the case where users include only parts of these datasets. Researchers will selectively utilize information from multiple studies, and create their own dataset to which they apply their analysis. As they can simply refer to other datasets, which are FDOs, a link between the datasets can automatically be derived. Furthermore, a researcher can be informed, as soon as updates, e.g., new study results he or she was using, are published.

Primary actor	Researcher
Input	Dataset (meta)data identifiers
Output	Link to the (new) FDO instance (dataset)
Brief description	The researcher is interested in different (parts of) datasets to answer her research question. Despite the fact that she does not need the complete studies, she also wants to ease the reproduction of her research so that interested researchers do not have to “pull” the parts of the datasets used in her experiment. As a result, she specifies the dataset parts of interest (including datasets as a whole is still possible) and creates her FDO based on these (meta)data.

Normal flow of events	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user selects (a set of) datasets: either searches for them and selects, or directly enters their identifiers. 2. Interface API provides a list of datasets to confirm. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. The interface “invokes” the “Create FDO” use case, with the selected datasets as input. 3. The user specifies the target storage solution for the resulting FDO. 4. The data repackaging competes and the user is displayed the resulting FDO instance.
Alternate flows	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1 The dataset identifiers the user provided cannot be found. The user is prompted to select datasets for repackaging. 1.2 Some of the datasets cannot be “repackaged” due to licensing or other limitations (publication embargo, etc.). The user is recommended to remove this/these dataset(s) before being able to complete the use case. 1.3 There is an issue with locating the target storage solution or the authentication. The use case prompts the users to specify the target storage solution or authentication credentials.

Table 4. Use case 3: Data repackaging at different granularity

Search FDO Using the API

This use case supports dataset search solely using the API. This is not meant to be a search frontend, but enable users to crawl and extract FDOs utilizing the different Metadata made available by an FDO and its inherent structure. Although modeled via an FDO and employing DOIP as communication means, the user is able to conduct the familiar search for a dataset of interest.

Primary actor	User or RDC
Input	Keywords or other search terms
Output	A list of matching FDOs (representing datasets)
Brief description	The user wants to search the KonsortSWD collection. She provides a search term, and receives a matching result list from the API. The user only gets metadata for each datasets based on the credentials she provides.
Normal flow of events	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user provides a search term 2. The API interface federates the search over the RDCs in KonsortSWD.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. The API collects the results to create the final result list. 4. The API returns the end result back to the user.
Alternate flows	

Table 5. Use case 4: Search for a dataset wrapped as an FDO

Single Sign On (SSO)

While having stated that the Single Sign On is not on our priority list, we would nonetheless shortly discuss its role within KonsortSWD. SSO is a “type of authentication in which a user logs in to one system and is automatically granted access to other services” (Kukic, 2017). Its adoption is primarily encouraged for environments where a user needs to use multiple services and authenticating with each individually becomes an issue. For KonsortSWD, the services and access policies that Research Data Centers have represent a good case to consider SSO.

This core feature enables a user to sign into the API using his own credentials of his/her employer. Afterwards, the user is able to perform actions on all the data sets in KonsortSWD, depending on the rights that are assigned to that user. This also allows for affiliation changes during the life-time of a researcher, re-using applied rights where applicable.

Primary actor	User who has the required credentials, such as the username and password.
Input	User credentials (username and password)
Output	Authentication and authorization acceptance or rejection
Brief description	The user wants to perform an operation that requires client authentication. For example, the user wants to access the data sets in KonsortSWD. KonsortSWD employs SSO to deliver this feature. The user uses his credentials such as username and password to authenticate to the interface API. Once accepted, the user does not need to provide her credentials for any of the activities with the interface.
Normal flow of events	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user uses his credentials to log into KonsortSWD. 2. For each of the FDOs (that represent datasets): <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. The API obtains the credential of that FDO from its credentials repository. b. The API authenticates itself to the FDO using the credentials. 3. The interface API returns an accept or reject to the end user (depending either on RDC or individual FDO criteria/permissions).
Alternate flows	3.1 The credential given by the user is not valid

	The API informs the user that his credentials are not valid and prompts the user to input the credential again.
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Table 6. Use case 5

Appendix II

Umfrage zum Forschungsdatenaustausch

Sehr geehrte Teilnehmerin, sehr geehrter Teilnehmer,

Diese Umfrage untersucht aktuelle Praktiken des Forschungsdatenaustauschs für Datenanbieter. Ihre Teilnahme ist von unschätzbarem Wert, da sie uns hilft, die datenbezogenen Bedürfnisse von Forschern zu verstehen.

Damit sie wissen worüber wir sprechen, übernehmen wir die Definition von Forschungsdaten gemäß der Deutschen Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG):

„Forschungsdaten können Messdaten, Laborwerte, audiovisuelle Informationen, Texte, Vermessungsdaten, Objekte aus Sammlungen oder Proben sein, die während wissenschaftlicher Arbeiten erstellt, entwickelt oder ausgewertet wurden. Methodische Testformen wie Fragebögen, Software und Simulationen können ebenfalls wichtige Ergebnisse für die wissenschaftliche Forschung liefern und sollten daher auch als Forschungsdaten eingestuft werden.“

Diese Umfrage ist anonym, da keine identifizierbaren Informationen gesammelt werden. Das Ausfüllen der Umfrage dauert ca. 10 Minuten.

Wir freuen uns sehr über Ihre Teilnahme. Füllen sie einfach den freien Platz zwischen den Fragen. Bei Ja / Nein, oder der Auswahl von Optionen, löschen sie einfach die betreffenden Zeilen, die nicht zutreffen.

Teil A: Allgemeine Informationen

1. Mit welchem KonsortSWD-Partner sind Sie verbunden?
 1. Leibniz-Informationszentrum Wirtschaft (ZBW)
 2. Das Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP)

3. Leibniz-Institut für Bildungsverläufe
 4. Leibniz-Institut für Bildungsforschung und Bildungsinformation (DIPF)
 5. Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften (GESIS)
2. Wie lange arbeiten Sie bereits im Aufgabenbereich Research Data Management (RDM)?
1. < 1 Jahr
 2. 2 - 5 Jahre
 3. 6 - 10 Jahre
 4. > 10 Jahre
3. Welche (berufliche) Rolle begleiten sie in Ihrer Organisation?
1. Kurator / Bibliothekar
 2. T-Spezialist (Softwarearchitekt, Entwickler, Datenbankentwickler und / oder -administrator, UI-Designer, Netzwerkadministrator / -ingenieur usw.)
 3. Forscher / Datenanalyst
 4. Andere Rolle (bitte angeben)

Teil B: Datenrepository

1. Verwendet Ihre Institution ein Forschungsdaten-Repository (RDR) für die RDM-Aktivitäten?
 Ja
 Nein
2. Falls ja, würden Sie sie bitte auflisten? Geben Sie außerdem an, ob das Repository im eigenen Haus oder mit Hilfe von einem Drittanbieter entwickelt wurde.

Repository (ggf. URL)	entwickelt / betrieben von

3. Welche Schnittstellen stellen sie dem Benutzer bereit?
 1. Web (HTML)
 2. RESTful API
 3. GraphQL
 4. Datenauszug per Datei
 5. Spezielles System, das physischen Zugriff erfordert
 6. Sonstige Schnittstelle (bitte angeben)

Teil C: Datenzugriff

1. Welche Daten Zugriffsmöglichkeiten unterstützt diese Schnittstelle(n)?
Geben Sie, bei mehr als einem dahinter liegenden Repository, dieses neben der entsprechenden Option an.
 1. alle verfügbaren Datensätze / Datensatzkataloge bereitstellen
 2. alle (Metadaten-) Beschreibungen für einen bestimmten Datensatz (basierend auf einer ID) bereitstellen
 3. verfügbarer Datensätze basierend auf bestimmten Kriterien (Datenanbieter, Institution, Domain usw.) bereitstellen
 4. Suchen von Datensätzen anhand bestimmter Kriterien
2. Welche Zugriffsgranularität unterstützt das oder diese Repositorien?
 1. Datensatz-Ebene: Abrufen von Datensätzen, basierend auf allgemeinen Metadatenelementen (Titel, Datum, Autor usw.)
 2. Domainspezifische Ebene: Bietet einen detaillierteren Zugriff, z. B. über Datensatzvariablen usw.
 3. Sonstige Ebene (bitte angeben)

Teil D: CRUD-Operationen (Data Create / Read / Update / Delete)

Die Schnittstelle unterstützt

1. (Meta-) Datenerstellung
2. (Meta-) Datenaktualisierung
3. (Meta-) Datenlöschung
4. Sonstige Operationen (bitte angeben)

Teil E: Zugangskontrolle

1. Ist eine Zugriffskontrolle auf das Datenrepository erforderlich?
Ja
Nein
2. Falls ja, für welche (Schnittstellen-) Aktivitäten oder Operationen ist dies erforderlich?
3. Welche Informationen werden für diese Aktivitäten benötigt, um die jeweilige Anfrage abzuschließen?

Teil F: Metadaten

1. Gibt es ein Metadatenschema, die die Datensätze in Ihrer Organisation beschreiben?
Wenn ja, um welches Schema handelt es sich?
2. Enthält das Repository eine Export- / Importmöglichkeit für Metadaten?
Falls ja, welche Metadatenelemente werden importiert?
Falls ja, welche Metadatenelemente werden exportiert?